

DEPLOYTOUR
European Tourism Data Space

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D4.4 Second quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR pilot implementation

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List of Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
DMO	Destination Management Organization
DPO	Data Product Offering
ETDS	European Tourism Data Space
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MICE	Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, and Exhibitions
MoU	Memoranda of Understanding
MVDS	Minimum Viable Data Space
OTA	Online Travel Agency
PMS	Property Management System
POI	Point of Interest
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package
WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4	Work Package 1, Work Package 2, Work Package 3, Work Package 4

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Executive Summary

This document, following a previous report on the activities from M1 (October 2024) to M13 (October 2025), presents the **first quarterly report on DEPLOYTOUR Pilot Implementation covering the period from M14 (November 2025) to M16 (January 2026)**. It provides an overview of progress across the five pilots, as well as coordination, technical and governance alignment, support, and monitoring activities under WP4.

The report documents advancements in pilot implementation conducted in close collaboration with WP2 (technical implementation) and WP3 (governance). It includes: i) an overview of the activities carried out for pilots' implementation and ii) a detailed progress analysis for each pilot.

The reporting period marks a **transition from initial structuring toward operational preparation**, particularly in terms of readiness assessment, governance formalisation, and technical onboarding planning.

Overview of the activities carried out for pilots' implementation

Pilot Coordination. During M14–M16, coordination efforts focused on operationalising a structured Pilot Action and Training Plan, validated during the November Consortium plenary meeting in Brussels. Particular emphasis was placed on completing the Readiness Assessment phase, enabling pilots to identify gaps in governance, technical preparedness, and data availability. Regular cross-pilot exchanges and structured alignment meetings strengthened collaboration and ensured consistency across implementation approaches.

Pilot Implementation. Significant progress was made in aligning pilot activities with both the technical and governance work streams. Regarding the **alignment with WP2 (Technical Group)**, pilots refined their Data Product Offerings (DPOs), clarified onboarding pathways, and prepared for connector deployment. Technical mentoring was initiated, and regular exchanges ensured coherence with the Minimum Viable Data Space (MVDS) - meaning the first version of the ETDS that will be deployed by the WP2 team - architecture and interoperability requirements. Regarding the **alignment with WP3 (Governance)**, governance integration advanced through the formalisation of Memos of Understanding (MoUs), clarification of roles and responsibilities, and dedicated governance training sessions. Identity management, trust frameworks, and policy definition were addressed to prepare pilots for compliant data exchange within ETDS.

Pilot Support. The Support Services framework evolved significantly during the reporting period, moving from conceptual guidance to hands-on accompaniment. The **Pilot Training Plan** delivered its first two phases (Readiness Assessment and Governance Integration), while preparation for the technical onboarding session (Phase 3 of the Action and Training Plan) began. The **Mentoring Programme** was formally launched, with technical and governance mentors assigned to each pilot and recurring coordination meetings were established. Finally, the **Living Q&A document** and other shared resources were updated to reflect emerging governance and technical questions.

Pilot Monitoring. The progress of the Use Cases (UC) was monitored through participation in monthly **pilot meetings** with partners and mentors from WP2 and WP3 and the **sharing of documents** (a Miro board showing the data exchanged and the progress of onboarding for each data provider and the Readiness Assessment document), which were constantly updated at the end of each month.

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Pilots' progress report

Overall, the project is progressing steadily, with **11 use cases under development** (7 under validation and 4 already validated), including the new full validation of the “Tourism and Business Traveller Observation in Île-de-France” use case in Pilot 3. By M16 (January 2026), the Pilots have significantly expanded their ecosystem, reaching the identification of **57 data providers and 94 datasets** identified for sharing (54 of which including non-open data). Of these, the data providers and the datasets confirmed are respectively 14 (50% more than in M13) and 37 (30% more than in M13), confirming both consolidation of ongoing discussions and advancement towards operational validation.

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1. Introduction

Purpose of the Document

This document serves as an activity progress report and aims to provide a detailed overview of the work carried out for the implementation of the **DEPLOYTOUR project Pilots** between **November 2025 (M14) and January 2026 (M16)**. The report focuses on the advancements of the five pilots:

- **Pilot 1:** Sustainable Tourism Management of Alpine Tourism
- **Pilot 2:** Mature Destination Resiliency and Competitiveness
- **Pilot 3:** MICE Sector Support
- **Pilot 4:** Leveraging Cultural Heritage to Diversify the Tourism Offer: The Case of Ano Syros (Greece)
- **Pilot 5:** Empowering SMEs in Tourism through a Collaborative TravelTech

In addition, the document reports on the coordination, support, and monitoring activities carried out by the partners of **Work Package 4 (WP4)** to ensure consistent Pilots implementation and alignment with the overall project goals. In doing so, it also underlines the strong collaboration and continuous exchanges with other Work Packages – particularly **WP2 (technical implementation)** and **WP3 (governance)** – which are essential both for the successful execution of the individual pilots and for the broader development of the **European Tourism Data Space (ETDS)**.

Structure of the Document

The document is divided into three main sections: the chapter on the overview of the activities carried out for pilots' implementation, the chapter on pilots' progress, and the conclusions.

Chapter “Overview of the activities carried out for pilots' implementation: M14-M16” presents a general overview of pilots' road towards complete implementation, describing coordination activities, the overall working plan followed by all pilot teams in coordination with technical and governance WPs, the support services developed and tested to assist the pilots in the process, and the monitoring and performance evaluation system structured and validated to ensure a flow of continuous measurement and feedback throughout the project.

Chapter “Pilots' Progress Report” outlines the progress achieved by each pilot between November 2025 (M14) and January 2026 (M16). A dedicated section is provided for each Pilot. Each section presents an overview of the activities carried out during the reporting period, with particular emphasis on stakeholder engagement and collaboration with WP2 (technical implementation) and WP3 (governance). It also provides updates on the Pilots use cases (UC), data providers, data consumers, and data sources, as well as a summary of the main risks identified and the corresponding mitigation measures.

The **conclusion** summarises the key elements of the report and outlines the next steps.

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Overview of the activities carried out for pilots' implementation: M14-M16

Pilot coordination

During the quarter M14-M16 (November 2025 – January 2026) the pilots have started to follow a detailed and structured implementation plan. The **Pilot Training Plan** has been developed together with the technical group of WP2, the governance group of WP3, WP6, and the project coordinator, to ensure its close alignment with both the technical and governance advancements and with the general timeline of DEPLOYTOUR, and to develop targeted training actions.

Table 1. Pilot Training Plan

Phase	Period	Training Objective	Audience	Training Activities	Materials / Tools	Expected Outcome
1. Readiness Assessment	Nov25-Dec25	Understand data space principles, onboarding process, and self-assessment methodology.	Pilots & WP leaders	Kick-off workshop, readiness checklist training, webinar on Data Space Onboarding.	Presentation deck, onboarding manual, readiness template.	Self-assessment completed and readiness gaps identified.
2. Identity & Governance Integration	Dec25-Jan26	Learn governance and identity management principles.	Pilots, WP Governance team	Workshop on trust frameworks, governance models, and access policies.	Governance framework, policy templates, recorded demo.	Trusted identities and governance documentation established.
3. Technical Onboarding (Connector, APIs, Access Policies)	Jan26-June26	Acquire technical knowledge to deploy connectors and integrate APIs.	Technical staff in pilots & WP technical team	Hands-on sessions, training on API exposure, helpdesk clinics.	Technical manuals, API docs, sandbox environment.	Operational connectors and secure APIs deployed.
4. Semantic & Legal Alignment (ODRL, Metadata, Contracts)	Feb26-Apr26	Understand semantic standards, metadata schemas, and legal compliance.	Pilots, legal & semantic experts	Seminar on metadata, legal clinic on ODRL and licensing, exercises.	Metadata guidelines, ODRL templates, example datasets.	Semantic alignment achieved and contracts validated.
5. Testing & Certification Support	Apr26-May26	Gain skills in testing, validation, and certification.	Pilots & technical WP	Simulated testing sessions, training on tools, certification workshop.	Test environment, checklists, report templates.	Certification readiness achieved.
6. Go-Live Enablement & Visibility	June26	Build capacity for deployment, communication, and monitoring.	Pilots & WP dissemination team	Go-live procedures training, communication workshop, KPI tracking webinar.	Go-live guide, monitoring dashboard, KPI template.	Pilots go live with visibility and reporting.
7. Post-Onboarding Support & Community Engagement	July26-Aug26	Develop skills for long-term operation and community participation.	All pilots & WP leads	Community meetings, advanced sessions, sustainability training.	Community platform, knowledge base, playbook.	Sustainable and active community participation.

The draft plan has been validated with the pilot teams during the Partners' Meeting held in Brussels on November 19th. Afterwards, the pilots have started working by following closely the plan. Mainly in M14 (November 2025) and M15 (December 2025), coordination efforts have

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been dedicated to ensuring that the pilots formalised their **readiness assessment (phase 1 of the plan)**, by compiling, revising and validating a self-assessment. From each pilot's self-assessment, it was possible to identify readiness gaps and take targeted decisions to ensure the success of each pilot implementation. Moreover, it was also ensured that training activities were conducted on time and followed the planned structure and topics. More on the training will be reported in the "Support services" paragraph.

Pilot implementation

Alignment with WP2 – Technical Group

The pilots are now preparing to start the **technical onboarding (phase 3 of the plan)**, in close coordination with WP2. In this advanced preparation phase, the liaison with the technical group has been constant and extended. In particular, pilots have continued updating the definition and scope of their DPOs (Data Product Offerings), crucial to inform and direct the technical onboarding. As part of the mentoring program (see paragraph "Support services" for more details), members of WP2 have started to actively participate in pilots' periodic meetings. During the reporting period, the possibility of installing five connectors was anticipated. This implied some changes within the Use Cases.

Alignment with WP3 – Governance

In coordination with WP3, WP4 has been working on pilot's **governance integration (Phase 2 of the plan)**. In particular, every pilot has had Memos of Understanding (MoUs) formally signed by all involved partners (Milestone MS5). Also, identity and governance issues have been the topic of targeted training. As part of the mentoring program (see paragraph "Support services" for more details), members of WP3 have started to actively participate in pilots' periodic meetings, to provide support to solve governance issues.

Support services

During the reporting period, activities under the Support Services framework focused on the **operational deployment of the Pilot Training Plan** and the formal launch of the **Mentoring Programme** as key milestones in the execution of the pilots.

Pilot Training Plan – Implementation Progress

Following the structured 7-Phase action plan (see table 1 for more details), the first two training phases were delivered.

- The **first training session** was delivered during the Plenary Meeting in Brussels. This session focused on the Readiness Assessment phase, providing pilots with a structured understanding of the self-assessment tool prepared in coordination with WP2 and WP3 leaders. A dedicated in-person working session was held during the plenary meeting, enabling direct interaction with pilots and allowing practical clarification of onboarding requirements. This face-to-face format significantly improved alignment and helped identify initial gaps and readiness levels across pilots. The objective of this first phase was not only awareness-building but also enabling pilots to position themselves within the onboarding journey and understand the expectations for the upcoming technical and governance phases.
- The **second training session** was delivered, focusing on governance-related topics, including: (i) Governance structures within data spaces, (ii) Roles and responsibilities, (iii) Policy definition, (iv) Legal and organisational considerations. This session responded to specific questions raised by pilots and addressed emerging governance challenges identified during Phase 1.

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During January, preparation began for the third training session, scheduled for February 2026. This session will focus on technical topics. The preparation phase includes alignment with WP2 technical progress to ensure that the content delivered reflects the current maturity level of the ETDS components.

Mentoring Programme

The Mentoring Programme was officially launched and put into operation across all pilots. Each pilot was informed of the technical and governance mentors assigned to support them, and they were asked to set up a recurring monthly coordination meeting in which the mentors are invited. These sessions are intended to help pilots address stalled topics, clarify doubts and concerns, and receive practical guidance, while also allowing mentors to gain a clear view of each pilot's progress and emerging needs. Several pilots have already held their first mentoring meetings during this period, while others have scheduled them to start in February.

Resources

Living Q&A Document (with all the answers to pilots' questions) was updated with a new dedicated section covering governance-related questions discussed during the training session. The updated version was shared with all pilots to ensure transparency and ongoing support. This continuous update mechanism strengthens the interactive and evolving nature of the Support Services Catalogue.

Monitoring and evaluation

An important part of pilots' implementation efforts is related to the monitoring and evaluation of their advancement.

To **monitor activities**, the team used two documents, updated on a monthly basis. Specifically, the first tool was the **Self-Readiness Assessment Report** (mentioned in paragraph "Pilot coordination"), which made it possible to assess the overall progress of the pilots, both from a technical and governance perspective. Secondly, a **Miro board** was used in which each pilot, for each Use Case, indicated the data provider, the data consumer, the need addressed, the data exchanged and the status of the exchange itself (from the hypothesis phase, to ongoing validation, to validation completed as defined in "Pilots' progress report" paragraph). This approach allowed all partners involved in WP4 and the pilots to remain constantly updated on progress.

To **evaluate pilots' progression**, the WP4 coordination team established the following Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):

- KPI 1: Total number of use cases identified,
- KPI 2: Total number of DATA PROVIDERS identified,
- KPI 3: Total number of DATASETS identified for sharing,
- KPI 4: Total number of DATASETS of NON-OPEN DATA identified for sharing.

The measures of each Pilot's KPIs are provided in the "Use Case KPIs" section of each Pilot's paragraph.

Overall, the project foresees the development of **11 use cases – 7 under validation and 4 already validated** (sum of KPI1 of each Pilot). During the period of analysis (M14-M16), Pilot 3 Use Case "Tourism and Business Traveller Observation in Île-de-France" reached full validation.

Regarding the number of data providers (KPI2)¹, by January 2026 (M16), **the Pilots overall identified 57 partners, 10 more compared to the previous reporting period**. Specifically, 19 (+11 in respect to M13) providers are in the phase "Just an hypothesis" since they have

¹ The number is counted as the sum of the data providers identified for each Pilot, meaning that – if the same provider is involved in more use cases – the provider is counted more than once.

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been identified by not yet engaged; 24 (-6) are in the phase “Ongoing validation” and have therefore been involved in a discussion, and 14 (+7) are in the phase “Completely validated” since they have agreed on sharing data for Pilot deployment. The decrease in data providers ongoing validation is mainly because some were discarded for several reasons such as Use Cases’ purpose fit, their technical ability to implement the connectors, or simply their willingness to share the data through the data space. In few cases (e.g. Pilot 5), the negative variation is due to the provider progress towards complete validation.

Regarding the number of datasets identified for sharing (KPI 3), by January 2026 (M16), **the Pilots overall identified 94 data sources, 12 more respect to the previous reporting period.** Specifically, 20 (+9 in respect to M13) datasets have been identified but not yet engaged, 37 (-8) have been under discussion, and 37 (+9) were confirmed to be used for Pilot deployment. The decrease in datasets ongoing validation is mainly explained by the fact that discussions led to datasets full approval, while in few cases (e.g. Pilot 1) datasets proved not to be relevant for Use Cases’ scope.

Regarding the total number of datasets of non-open data identified for sharing (KPI4), which is a subset of the overall number of data sources, by January 2026 (M16), **the pilots overall identified 54 data sources, 18 more respect to the previous reporting period.** Specifically, 19 (+13 in respect to M13) datasets have been identified but not yet engaged, 30 (+4) have been under discussion, and 5 (+1) were confirmed to be used for Pilot deployment. The increase in non-open data datasets ongoing validation is driven by Pilot 3, where all the datasets include non-open data.

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Pilots' progress report

This chapter presents the progress achieved by each Pilot between November 2025 (M14) and January 2026 (M16). Each Pilot section opens with a **summary of its respective Use Cases** and is structured into the following sub-sections:

- **“Activities carried out and stakeholder involvement”** provides an overview of the main activities undertaken during the reporting period, with particular emphasis on stakeholder engagement and collaboration with WP2 (technical implementation) and WP3 (governance) teams.
- **“Use case updates”** outlines updates related to the scope of the use cases, as well as developments concerning data providers, data consumers, and data sources. Data sources refer to the datasets to be exchanged through the data space and required for the deployment of the use cases.
- **“Use case KPIs”** offers a quantitative overview of progress in terms of use cases, data providers, and data sources, in terms of datasets identified for sharing and including the detail for non-open data. For each KPI, the summary table details the development status of the respective elements, according to the following categories:
 - **Just hypothesis:** data providers and consumers have not yet been contacted.
 - **Ongoing validation:** data providers and consumers have been contacted, but their participation has not yet been confirmed.
 - **Completely validated:** all data providers and consumers have agreed to participate, and data sharing conditions have been agreed upon.
 - **Onboarding completed:** the data is available in the catalogue.
 - **Data sharing completed:** data exchange is actively ongoing or completed.
 - **“Risks and mitigation strategies”** summarises the main risks identified or anticipated by the Pilot team, along with the mitigation measures put in place to address them.

Pilot 1: Sustainable Tourism Management of Alpine Tourism

Use Case 1 – FLOWS Julian Alps (UC1) focuses on the reuse and integration of cross border statistical tourism datasets within the FLOWS platform to support sustainable tourism management in the Julian Alps. The use case builds on available historical data provided by cross border statistical offices. These datasets will be harmonised and reused within FLOWS to generate cross-border dashboard to monitor visitor flows.

By enabling structured data sharing and interoperability, UC1 enhances the analytical capacity of the existing platform and supports coordinated decision-making among cross border DMOs, municipalities, and tourism authorities. The reuse of statistical data allows for improved peak-season management, better coordination during major events, and more efficient infrastructure planning. The cross-border dimension ensures comparability of data and facilitates scalable, data-driven tourism management across the Alpine region.

Use Case 2 – Sustainability Scoring for Alpine Tours (UC2) develops a cross-border sustainability scoring model for Alpine tours, supporting environmentally responsible visitor behaviour. The use case emerged from identified gaps in harmonised sustainability information and confirmed technical feasibility for integrating environmental, mobility, and tourism data. Stakeholder engagement validated the demand for a shared scoring model, API-based integration, and comparative dashboards.

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Activities carried out and involvement of stakeholders

During M14–M16, Pilot 1 advanced cross-border data-driven tools for sustainable tourism in the Julian Alps region in two areas: visitor management (UC1) and a Digital Sustainability Calculator for alpine tours (UC2). Regular partner meetings ensured strategic alignment, monitored progress and addressed cross-border coordination challenges. After the mentoring programme with partners from WP2 and WP3 has been established, the allocated mentors have been invited to regular bi-weekly meetings.

Initially, five Data Product Offerings (DPOs) were defined to support both use cases. Sample datasets for cross-border arrivals and stays were identified and validated using data from Statistical Office Slovenia and Carinthia (Landesstelle für Statistik Kärnten). Engagement with main local stakeholders was conducted through various channels (in-person meetings and on-line calls).

In parallel, UC2 consolidated the scope and objectives, defined as an API-based service assessing hiking tours across ecological, social and economic dimensions. Tyrol was set as pilot region, with Triglav and Dobratsch as control regions. Data sources were identified and assessed, including INSPIRE datasets, environmental and weather data, tour and trail networks, accident statistics, tourism infrastructure and mobility-related datasets, with emphasis on data quality and interoperability. The API design, input/output definitions and data formats were specified, and deployment within the Tourism Data Space was prepared. Bilateral exchanges with technology providers, initiatives and state departments supported validation of assumptions, identification of data gaps and discussion of implementation risks. Ongoing coordination between Austria Tourism and Know-Center ensured iterative refinement of indicators, model logic and implementation priorities.

Use case updates

Number and scope of Use Cases

During the reporting period, no changes occurred regarding the number or overall scope of use cases within Pilot 1. The pilot continues to consist of two use cases (UC1 and UC2), both remaining in a phase of ongoing technical and organisational consolidation. The implementation strategy foresees starting with a limited number of Data Product Offerings (DPOs) to be validated within the data space.

Data Providers

For UC1 (Cross-Border Visitor Management), the identified data providers are Arctur, Data Appeal, and Trenitalia. Arctur plays a dual role, acting not only as a provider but also as a data consumer. The number of active data providers is still subject to consolidation.

At the beginning of the project, we had foreseen more data providers, but due to the number of available connectors per pilot and also limited technical capabilities of the data providers, we decided to take different approach and shorten the list of potential data providers, however it could be expanded in later phases.

For UC2 (Digital Sustainability Calculator for Alpine Tours), the identified data providers include Austria Tourism, Know Center, Geosphere (alternatively Kachelmann), the Austrian Board for Alpine Safety, and various national and federal Open Data and Geoportals.

Data Consumers

In UC1, Arctur also acts as a data consumer, leveraging Data Appeal's event and OTA-related datasets to enhance cross-border visitor management insights. The final number of active data consumers is still under consolidation.

In UC2, data consumers consist of B2C platforms integrating sustainability scores via API (such as tour planning and outdoor applications), as well as B2B stakeholders, including

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DMOs, protected area managers, and regional authorities, who use the data to support sustainable tourism planning and management.

Data Sources

For UC1, relevant data sources include Arctur’s trail visits data (real-time and historical open data), harmonised cross-border arrivals and stays statistics, proprietary event and OTA data from Data Appeal, and Trenitalia’s proprietary data on train services, timetables, and timetables of tourist trains.

For UC2, data sources comprise tourism infrastructure data, harmonised cross-border statistics, overnight stays forecasts, calculated tourism KPIs, weather data, alpine accident statistics, and INSPIRE datasets on natural areas.

Use case KPIs

The commented Table below provides Pilot’s KPIs measures in M13, M16 and their variation incurred in the quarter.

Table 2. KPIs (Pilot 1)

	M13 (D4.2)	M16 (D4.4)	Variation
KPI 1: Total number of use cases identified	2	2	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	0	0	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	2	2	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
KPI 2: Total number of DATA PROVIDERS identified	16	7	-9
<i>Data providers in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	4	0	-4
<i>Data providers in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	10	5	-5
<i>Data providers in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	2	2	0
<i>Data providers in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Data providers in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
KPI 3: Total number of DATASETS identified for sharing	16	8	-8
<i>Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	3	0	-3
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	11	6	-5
<i>Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	2	2	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
KPI 4: Total number of DATASETS of NON-OPEN DATA identified for sharing	7	4	-3
<i>Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	2	0	-2
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	3	2	-1
<i>Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	2	2	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0

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Variations explanations:

The changes in KPIs are related to the limited number of available data space connectors per pilot (at the time this report has been written are estimated in 5 per pilot). Therefore, the pilot reduced the number of DPOs to support both use cases. Additionally, initially, it was foreseen to implement connectors directly to the providers of statistical data, however, the raw data needs to be processed, cleaned and harmonised before it can be used. Therefore, Arctur decided to directly access the data, clean it, and prepare a single DPO.

While KPI 1 remained unchanged since last period reporting (M13), the others varied.

The **number of data providers** (KPI2) is still in the process of consolidation, with 5 providers undergoing validation (Arctur, Know Center, Geosphere (alternatively Kachelmann), the Austrian Board for Alpine Safety, and Trenitalia) and 2 providers already validated (Austria Tourism, Data Appeal). Other initially identified data providers (9) were discarded to focus on most appropriate data providers, that fit the purpose of use cases and have the technical ability to implement the connectors and are willing to share the data through the data space.

Similarly, the **number of datasets identified for sharing** (KPI3) is progressing in validation, with 6 datasets progressing and 2 already validated. The datasets are:

- In “Ongoing validation” phase:
 - Harmonised cross-border statistical data on tourist arrivals and stays (validating sample data from 3 cross-border regions).
 - Trail visits (to validate if only historical data or real-time data requires two different connectors).
 - Tour data.
 - Train services.
- As “Completely validated”
 - Event data, OTA saturation (to discuss technical implementation).

The 3 datasets identified as “just hypothesis” in M13 were discarded to focus on the most appropriate datasets, that fit the purpose of both use cases, while the other 5 identified as “ongoing validation” were discarded due to the reason mentioned above.

The **total number of DATASETS of NON-OPEN DATA identified for sharing** (KPI4) is now 4, 2 “ongoing validation” (DPO5a – train services, DPO5b – train timetables) and 2 already validated (DPO3a – event data, DPO3b - OTA saturation data). Other identified non-open data sets - in total 3 – were discarded to focus on the most appropriate data sets, that fit the purpose of both use cases.

Risks and mitigation strategies

Key risks relate to data availability and quality, especially for real-time data, as well as governance and liability aspects. These risks are mitigated through an iterative, modular approach, prioritising reliable data sources, transparent scoring logic and continuous stakeholder engagement and collaboration with WP2 and WP3.

Risk 1: Limited Data Interoperability and Legal Constraints

UC1 depends on integrating cross-border datasets (arrivals and stays, OTA data) from different providers and countries. Key risks are differences in data standards, formats and update cycles; incomplete harmonisation of statistical methodologies across regions; legal and contractual restrictions related to proprietary data. If not managed carefully, this could delay DPO validation or limit the usability of the cross-border dataset within the data space.

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Impact: Medium–High (direct effect on operationalisation of DPO).
Mitigation: Early alignment on data models, clear data-sharing agreements, prioritisation of high-quality datasets for the first validation phase and collaboration with WP2 and WP3.

Risk 2: Data Quality and Indicator Validity

The sustainability calculator relies on multiple heterogeneous datasets (weather, accident statistics, tourism KPIs, infrastructure, INSPIRE data). Key risks are gaps or inconsistencies in environmental and safety data; limited granularity of regional statistics; challenges in translating available data into robust, scientifically credible sustainability indicators.

Mitigation: Iterative validation with stakeholders, transparent methodology, prioritisation of indicators with reliable data coverage and collaboration with WP2 and WP3.

Pilot 2: Mature Destination Resiliency and Competitiveness

During the reporting period, Pilot 2 progressed from use case definition toward early operationalisation, consolidating both methodological and technical foundations across Andalusia (UC1) and the Balearic Islands (UC2). The pilot continues to address resilience, sustainability, and competitiveness in mature destinations through the integration of sustainability indicators with operational, marketing, and official statistical data, aligned with European Tourism Data Space (ETDS) principles.

- **Use Case 1 (Andalusia):** applies Turismo de Andalucía’s sustainability indicator framework, operationalising it within a campaign monitoring and activation system that enables sustainability-based marketing and promotion, integrating operational (PMS), sustainability and marketing signals. It is supported by AdQuiver’s adtech/tourism intelligence capabilities and aligned with European interoperability and data-sharing requirements, with validation through engagement with local DMOs and tourism SMEs.
- **Use Case 2 (Balearic Islands):** delivers a near real-time **impact monitoring** approach across four dimensions (**Economic | Social | Environmental | Territorial**), integrating heterogeneous datasets into dashboards to support more adaptive and evidence-based destination management.

Activities carried out and involvement of stakeholders

During the quarter, Pilot 2 advanced from “definition/validation” into more concrete operationalisation steps across both regions.

In UC1 (Andalusia), Turismo de Andalucía worked closely with AdQuiver and consortium partners to align the “sustainable tourist” approach with a concrete, data-driven activation logic. A workflow was defined in which campaign outputs can inform a shared decision framework (e.g. identifying viable destinations, segments, and source markets). In parallel, a digital-marketing-led data audit was conducted to consolidate the key inputs needed to operationalise the “sustainable tourist” concept and support evidence-based market and destination choices. Activities centred on methodological consolidation rather than campaign execution, including: (i) agreeing a limited set of pilot destinations to reduce operational risk; (ii) assessing priority source markets and constraints (seasonality, maturity, behavioural patterns); and (iii) validating a pragmatic approach to creatives and landing pages to ensure traceability and data-capture readiness.

In the Balearic Islands (UC2), the consortium consolidated and expanded the stakeholder base by involving **additional private tourism companies**, strengthening the set of providers and improving data readiness. In parallel, the team defined **two operational scenarios** reflecting stakeholder needs, while keeping the Use Case vision consistent: monitoring and

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positively influencing sustainability across the **four impact axes (economic, social, environmental, territorial)**.

Exchanges with the technical group WP2 remained continuous with weekly meetings, ensuring alignment with architectural choices and interoperability requirements. Pilot 2 contributed directly to feasibility by confirming a **FIWARE + EDC-based data space deployment**, enabling data onboarding pathways for both use cases and their providers. In governance, work with WP3 progressed through signature/confirmation of agreements with data providers and pre-definition of roles and rules for data federation between Data Spaces in the case of Balearics, with the understanding that finalisation must align with high-level European Tourism Data Space governance requirements for UC's data sharing.

Use case updates

Number and scope of Use Cases

The Pilot continues with **two use cases** (UC1 Andalusia; UC2 Balearic Islands), with scope refined through implementation-driven detailing rather than conceptual changes. UC1's progress focused on strengthening readiness for upcoming activations by clarifying the minimum viable inputs, governance assumptions and measurement requirements. UC2 progressed by consolidating the regional ecosystem and translating stakeholder needs into **two defined scenarios** to guide dashboard design, alerting/threshold logic, and decision workflows across the four sustainability axes.

Data providers

In Andalusia, Turismo de Andalucía remains the main provider of destination first-party inputs, while engagement has been initiated with ISTAC (Canary Islands Statistical Institute) to explore the public-sector/governance-level incorporation of the Canary Islands (coordination initiated); the Balearic Islands increased engagement of private-sector actors and reinforced provider commitment and availability, improving the robustness of the provider network and providing the 'how-to onboard' documentation.

Data consumers

For both UC1 and UC2, the main consumers remain DMOs, public authorities, and tourism SMEs; In addition, for UC2, the scenario definition clarified how different institutional units and technical teams consume indicators for adaptive management.

Data sources

A key update in this period is the increased specificity of UC1 data sources: destination web/CRM and landing data, harmonised tracking standards (GA4/UTMs/naming), and the minimum set of paid-media platform delivery signals (e.g., impressions, clicks, spend, conversions/value) to be captured consistently once activations begin (activations have not started yet in this reporting period; PMS data access remains a later-phase item subject to access and governance). UC2 advanced through broader private-sector participation and refined operational indicators.

Technically, the FIWARE/EDC deployment decision improves interoperability feasibility and provider onboarding pathways.

Use case KPIs

The commented Table below provides Pilot's KPIs measures in M13, M16 and their variation incurred in the quarter.

Table 3. KPIs (Pilot 2)

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	M13 (D4.2)	M16 (D4.4)	Variation
KPI 1: Total number of use cases identified	2	2	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	0	0	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	0	0	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	2	2	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
KPI 2: Total number of DATA PROVIDERSFB identified	12	14	+2
<i>Data providers in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	1	0	-1
<i>Data providers in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	6	7	+1
<i>Data providers in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	5	7	+2
<i>Data providers in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Data providers in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
KPI 3: Total number of DATASETS identified for sharing	42	43	+1
<i>Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	4	1	-3
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	12	15	+3
<i>Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	26	27	+1
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
KPI 4: Total number of DATASETS of NON-OPEN DATA identified for sharing	14	14	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	0	0	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	13	13	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	1	1	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0

Variations explanations:

Quantitative KPIs remain stable (no net new use cases/providers/datasets reported in the table), while progress is reflected in qualitative maturity: UC1 inputs were consolidated through a digital-marketing data audit, tracking standards were aligned (GA4/UTMs), and additional official statistics for the Canary Islands will be explored via ISTAC; stronger UC2 private-sector involvement and scenario definition, and clearer technical/governance alignment enabling the next step toward onboarding and data sharing.

Risks and mitigation strategies

These are some of the risk and mitigation propositions for the pilot improvement.

Risk: Slower onboarding/data sharing (especially proprietary datasets).

Mitigation: Establish phased onboarding plans per provider prioritising “ready” feeds first and use of common templates for agreements and technical checklists.

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Risk: Governance finalisation pending ETDS high-level rules.

Mitigation: Pilot 2 partners will interim governance roles/rules as “pre-defined” and run alignment checkpoints with WP3 to ensure downstream compliance.

Risk: Interoperability/technology adoption complexity for providers.

Mitigation: Coordination with WP2, partners will provide reference deployment patterns and clear integration pathways via FIWARE/EDC

Risk: Stakeholder fatigue / uneven engagement across regions.

Mitigation: Keep on scenario-based working sessions (UC2) and specific, well-instrumented DMO activations (once activations start) to make value tangible and actionable for participants (UC1).”

Risk: Sensitive private-sector data (specifically, in UC1, hotels and PMS may be restricted by commercial confidentiality and privacy requirements, delaying access or limiting granularity).

Mitigation: start with aggregated/anonymised outputs and a minimal dataset under clear access controls/terms, then expand once governance safeguards are validated.

Pilot 3 - Supporting the MICE competitiveness in île de France

Pilot 3 aims to strengthen the **competitiveness of the MICE (Meetings, Incentives, Conferences and Exhibitions) sector in Île-de-France.**

The Paris region relies heavily on business tourism. However, the sector faces several challenges: a fragmented data ecosystem, limited comprehensive insights into business traveller behaviour and trends, a lack of real-time monitoring to support agile decision-making, and increasing demand for hyper-personalised experiences, including “bleisure” (the combination of business and leisure travel).

To address these challenges, the pilot develops concrete use cases designed to support local stakeholders through:

- **Holistic sector intelligence:** Delivering clear, up-to-date insights tailored to stakeholders’ needs.
- **Enhanced visitor understanding:** Generating deeper knowledge of visitor profiles, behaviours, satisfaction levels and journey patterns to better tailor services.
- **Data-driven decision-making:** Enabling more effective strategies and policies based on reliable and shared data.

Through close collaboration with MICE stakeholders and local actors, the pilot seeks to enhance existing solutions by fostering data sharing and cooperation. The identified Use Cases are:

- **Use Case 1 – Data on Seminars and Business Events in Hotel Structures:** Improving knowledge of professional events – such as congresses, meetings and seminars – hosted in hotels across Île-de-France.
- **Use Case 2 – Tourism and Business Traveller Observation in Île-de-France:** Supporting Choose Paris Region in strengthening tourism observation. This begins with accurate data on visitor flows arriving by air, rail and road, followed by refined segmentation of MICE travellers to better understand their behaviours, economic impact and overall contribution, drawing on a broader range of data providers.
- **Use Case 3 – Compliance with Event ISO Standards:** Facilitating compliance with ISO event standards through data-driven certification processes. EXPO’STAT, a leading event auditing company (auditing over 650 events annually), aims to improve data verification and securely share certificates via the DEPLOYTOUR data space. In parallel, it is developing new data products based on aggregated event insights and is

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currently seeking data consumers. At this stage, the focus is primarily on sharing these new data products rather than on certificate exchange.

Activities carried out and involvement of stakeholders

From November 2025 (M14) to January 2026 (M16), EONA-X participated in **two stakeholder workshops** to present the concept of data sharing through a data space and introduce Pilot 3 (MICE). These workshops aimed to explain the pilot's implementation in Île-de-France and demonstrate its scalability to other destinations.

The **first workshop** was organized by the European Exhibition Industry Alliance in Brussels and gathered around 25 participants, representing approximately 10 European exhibition centres including Paris île de France. Attendees also included Data & Research Specialists, Data Analysts, Research Directors, and Digital Strategy Managers. This workshop provided an opportunity to explain the pilot's objectives and showcase its potential for broader application.

The **second workshop** was organized by NECSTouR in Brussels at the ToT Lab Data Summit in December. It focused on presenting Pilot 3, specifically Use Case 2, with Choose Paris Region, to DMOs. This session was a great opportunity to share experiences not only from EONA-X's perspective but also from the destination we are currently collaborating with, helping them address their data-sharing challenges through Pilot 3. Choose Paris Region has since officially joined EONA-X data space.

Discussions and meetings are still ongoing with Atout France and Expo'stat to deploy their specific Use Case. The difficulty being the consent of Expo'stat clients before sharing or the need for Expo'stat to aggregate data into general insights (requiring internal data management capacities). The current aim is to find several potentially interested data consumers for Expo'stat's data insights or to get major event organizers consents for Expo'stat to expose certificates to Atout France.

The most advanced use case, with clearly identified data providers and consumer, is the one involving Choose Paris Region, with whom the kick off meeting of the use case was held in January.

Engagement with the technical group (WP2) has been supportive, particularly regarding two aspects: the proposal of offering connectors per pilot with no extra charge for the duration of the project, which has facilitated discussions with local stakeholders, and first discussions about future interoperability between EONA-X and the Minimum Viable Data Space (MVDS). This perspective means that actors within the MVDS should be able to exchange data with the EONA-X ecosystem, and vice versa, opening new possibilities for data-sharing and a reinforced role of the upcoming European Tourism Data Space in Pilot 3.

Use case updates

Number and scope of use cases

The number and scope of the use cases remain unchanged for now. We are currently prioritizing Use Case 2, as it is the most advanced at this stage and has a shorter deadline. Scopes are refined throughout the implementations.

Concerning UC1, the data consumer, Atout France, provided us with clear specifications regarding the data sources they wish to access. However, it seems that data on the number of business events held in hotels in the Île-de-France region is not centralised. Instead, each hotel manages its own data individually.

As a result, we are exploring alternative approaches to access this data, including reaching out to new stakeholders, such as platforms for booking meeting rooms in hotels and Property Management System (PMS) providers.

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Concerning UC2, specific data products have been identified, including datasets from SNCF and Aéroports de Paris. We are currently in discussions with these stakeholders to define the datasets and terms and conditions for data access.

Finally, for UC3, Expo’stat is in the process of developing relevant data products based on the data they collect from event organisers. Once these data products are finalised, we will explore how to integrate them into the ETDS catalogue. In the meantime, we are engaging with potential data consumers to prepare for future data exchange.

Data providers

For **UC1**, Atout France shared a list of 18 potential data providers, including hotel groups such as Accor, Best Western, and Louvre Hotels. We have contacted some of them but are struggling to determine whether they are willing to share occupancy rates and the number of business events held in their hotels. For this reason, they remain in the "hypothesis" column in the table below.

For **UC2**, Choose Paris Region provided a precise list of data providers during our kick-off meeting in January. Therefore, we are currently planning meetings with SNCF, Aéroports de Paris (ADP), and Data Appeal to determine the relevant data products they would need to complete data they are collecting from their surveys.

For **UC3**, the data provider is Expo’stat. They are developing relevant data products based on the data they collect from event organisers.

Data consumers

Atout France is the consumer of the UC1, Choose Paris of the UC2 and we are defining which entities would be willing to consume Expo’stat insights for UC3.

Data sources

No major changes have occurred in the overall categories of data sources. For now, we are focusing on the data providers and planning meetings so they can meet with the data consumers and define the datasets they would like to consume.

Finally, form a **technical point of view**, coordination with WP2 remained ongoing to ensure the pilot development stays aligned with technological solutions, architectural decisions, and overall technical progress within DEPLOYTOUR, supporting future interoperability and onboarding pathways.

Use case KPIs

The commented Table below provides Pilot’s KPIs measures in M13, M16 and their variation intercurred in the quarter.

Table 4. KPIs (Pilot 3)

	M13 (D4.2)	M16 (D4.4)	Variation
KPI 1: Total number of use cases identified	3	3	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	0	0	
<i>Use cases in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	3	2	-1
<i>Use cases in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	0	1	+1
<i>Use cases in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	
<i>Use cases in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	
KPI 2: Total number of DATA PROVIDERS identified	3	22	+19

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	M13 (D4.2)	M16 (D4.4)	Variation
Data providers in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS	1	19	+18
Data providers in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION	2	1	-1
Data providers in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED	0	2	+2
Data providers in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED	0	0	0
Data providers in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED	0	0	0
KPI 3: Total number of DATASETS identified for sharing	3	25	+22
Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS	1	19	+18
Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION	2	6	+4
Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED	0	0	0
Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED	0	0	0
Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED	0	0	0
KPI 4: Total number of DATASETS of NON-OPEN DATA identified for sharing	3	25	+22
Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS	1	19	+18
Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION	2	6	+4
Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED	0	0	0
Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED	0	0	0
Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED	0	0	0

Variations explanations:

- The **UC2** (KPI1) moved from "**ongoing validation**" to "**completely validated**" after we held the kick-off meeting in January, identified data providers, and are now setting up meetings to discuss the data products to be exchanged and their terms and conditions.
- Regarding **data providers** (KPI2), 19 have been added. For UC1, Atout France shared a list of 18 identified data providers (hotels). Since we are still in the process of contacting them, they remain in the "just hypothesis" status. For UC2, we have also identified Trenitalia, but we are not yet in discussions with them regarding this Use Case.
The "ongoing validation" status also changed, as SNCF and ADP moved to "completely validated" and Data Appeal was added. Therefore, two data providers (ADP and SNCF) are now in the "completely validated" category, as discussions are ongoing.
- Regarding **datasets** (KPI3 and 4), 22 have been added: one dataset per hotel identified by Atout France, plus one dataset for Trenitalia. We are currently discussing ("ongoing validation") 6 datasets with Data Appeal, ADP, and SNCF to identify the most relevant datasets for UC2, 4 of these (2 from SNCF and 2 from ADP) are new in respect to M13.
- Finally, **so far, we are only discussing non-open datasets** as open-data is already available to stakeholders and a "nice to have" in a data space at a later stage.

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Risks and mitigation strategies

During this period, we encountered the withdrawal of Amadeus from WP4 (December 2025). Amadeus, a partner in Pilot 3, has expressed the wish to revoke its commitment in PMs for the pilot 3 while staying an active partner in the DEPLOYTOUR consortium. EONA-X, as leaders of Pilot 3, have asked if a contribution in data might be envisioned (at business and administrative level) and are currently waiting for an answer to this risk mitigation plan. This solution, if feasible, could concretely support the pilot.

1.1 Pilot 4 - Leveraging cultural heritage to diversify tourism offer: the case of Ano Syros (Greece)

Pilot 4 uses Ano Syros (Greece)—a medieval hill settlement with rich heritage but strong seasonality and accessibility constraints—as a demonstrator of how the European Tourism Data Space (ETDS) can help shift a “sea & sun” destination toward a more sustainable, year-round cultural heritage model. The pilot combines digitised cultural heritage assets (e.g., 3D photorealistic models/digital twins and mapped routes from previous digitisation work) with complementary tourism datasets (e.g., tourism POIs, OTA price signals, and visitor/human-density insights) to: (1) improve accessibility and support heritage preservation priorities, (2) design engaging cultural experiences (including immersive/VR-ready assets) and (3) build stronger narratives and storytelling to reshape the destination image beyond peak-summer tourism. The overall intent is a replicable approach for other European heritage destinations seeking tourism diversification and cross-sector interoperability.

Activities carried out and involvement of stakeholders

During this quarter, the approach to onboarding cultural heritage data from the [5D-ARCH-AID project](#)—including 3D data, 360° images, and related assets—was revised. Following project-level guidance to streamline onboarding and ensure discoverability within the European Tourism Data Space, these assets will be published as ETDS Data Product Offerings and made available through the ETDS catalogue, while keeping clear attribution to the original source and maintaining alignment with Cultural Heritage domain standards for future cross-space federation.

In Pilot 4, we reviewed the Data Product Offerings, the involved data providers and the data consumers to ensure consistency with the evolving technical onboarding and governance guidance.

As a result, the Pleiades cluster will operate as the main ETDS technical participant, enabling it to (i) publish selected Pilot 4 data products (including those originating from cluster members and, where needed, on behalf of external data owners that are not operating an ETDS connector), and (ii) consume complementary data products also from other providers (e.g., The Data Appeal Company, Europeana). This means Pleiades may appear as both *provider* and *consumer*, but always for different counterparties (i.e., not “sharing data with itself”). In alignment with WP3 and ETDS governance policies, a Memo of Understanding was signed to clearly define the contributions of each partner of Pilot 4.

Recent **stakeholder meetings** (with the same core groups engaged since D4.2—cultural organisations, tourism SMEs, and the local municipality) focused on technical refinements for the implementation phase, particularly the specifications of targeted end applications per use case. These discussions also supported the finalisation of the Data Product Offerings. In parallel, consultations with two regional cultural organisations helped confirm the long-term sustainability approach for the use cases and addressed previously identified feasibility constraints.

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Questions and concerns from pilot partners have been collected in preparation for monthly mentor meetings, with the first session held during the second half of February. Currently, the Pilot team is working in close coordination with WP2 in order for the data providers and the data consumers of the Pilot to understand what the technical process for onboarding will be. In parallel, along with WP3, the team is also trying to understand the process of onboarding from the governance side and which actions, rules etc. should be followed by the data providers and consumers.

Use case updates

Number and scope of Use Cases

From November 2025 to January 2026, the total number of designed Use Cases remained unchanged, since the last deliverable (D4.2) at three (2 ongoing validation + 1 validated). During this period, progress was made through the finalization of the required Data Product Offerings (DPOs), data providers, and data consumers. The maturity of both the DPOs and the final applications increased significantly.

Data providers

This quarter’s discussions with data providers focused on validating the details of data to be used. Meetings with Data Appeal, which will act as a data provider for Pilot 4, provided insights into technical specifications regarding data sharing and highlighted aspects of geographical accuracy that require further investigation. Technical aspects related to the format and metadata model of the DPOs were also addressed.

The DPOs discussed included:

- Human Density Mapping dataset
- Tourism Points of Interest (POIs)
- OTA Prices Data pack

Data Appeal clarified that they cannot provide Weather Data, which led to the exclusion of the proposed DPO of as a nonmandatory data pack for the implementation of Pilot 4. Additionally, the data provider of Syros Agenda was removed from the list of potential providers, as the dataset is open-source and online, and the provider was reluctant to create an ETDS connector. Consequently, the Culture Event data DPO was deemed unnecessary for the evolution phase of Pilot 4.

Data Consumers

During this quarter, the definition of Data Consumers progressed with ARCTUR identified as one of the Data Consumers for Use Case 2. Meetings highlighted ARCTUR’s key contributions, including the reuse of 3D model datasets to develop tools for VR/MR heritage applications, and validated the objectives of Use Case 2.

Data Sources

No major changes occurred in the overall categories of data sources, although the total number of required DPOs decreased. The focus shifted toward increasing the maturity of Pilot 4 and the mandatory DPOs. Selected datasets were further validated in terms of availability, governance guidelines, and relevance within each use case. Pleiades’ role as a data provider for onboarding 3D data ensures that fewer than six connectors will be needed for the implementation of the three Pilot 4 use cases.

Technical alignment

Coordination with WP2 continued throughout the quarter to ensure that use case development remains aligned with technological solutions, architectural decisions, and overall technical progress within DEPLOYTOUR, supporting future interoperability and onboarding pathways.

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Use case KPIs

The commented Table below provides Pilot’s KPIs measures in M13, M16 and their variation intercurrent in the quarter.

Table 5. KPIs (Pilot 4)

	M13 (D4.2)	M16 (D4.4)	Variation
KPI 1: Total number of use cases identified	3	3	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	0	0	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	2	2	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	1	1	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
KPI 2: Total number of DATA PROVIDERS identified	5	3	-2
<i>Data providers in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	0	0	0
<i>Data providers in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	5	2	-3
<i>Data providers in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	0	1	+1
<i>Data providers in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Data providers in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
KPI 3: Total number of DATASETS identified for sharing	10	7	-3
<i>Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	1	0	-1
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	9	4	-5
<i>Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	0	3	+3
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
KPI 4: Total number of DATASETS of NON-OPEN DATA identified for sharing	4	3	-1
<i>Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	1	0	-1
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	2	3	+1
<i>Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	1	0	-1
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0

Regarding the maturity of the two Use Cases still in validation mode during the period between D4.2 and D4.4 and what is required for them to reach the state of complete validation: for UC2 the detailed technical specifications from Data Appeal are expected to seal their DPOs; for UC3 there are several pending issues to be specified in order to evaluate the feasibility of organising a hackathon for the implementation of UC.

The Pilot 4 DPO portfolio is *streamlined* around the core, mandatory offerings (Human Density Mapping, Tourism POIs, and OTA Prices), while two previously “nice-to-have” offerings—**DPO 05 (Weather Forecast of Ano Syros)** and **DPO 09 (Cultural Event Schedule of Ano Syros)**

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— have been explicitly downgraded to **non-mandatory**. This reprioritisation constitutes the main driver behind the deltas presented in Table 5.

With respect to DPO 05 (Weather Forecast of Ano Syros), the **Weather Data dataset** was initially planned to be sourced from OpenWeatherMap. However, as the use case matured, this dataset was reclassified from mandatory to “nice-to-have.” Subsequently, it was clarified that any external data provider must support integration through an available connector in order to supply data to the ETDS. As onboarding OpenWeatherMap under these technical requirements was not feasible, this option was discontinued. Data Appeal was then examined as a potential alternative provider; however, they confirmed that they were unable to supply the required weather dataset. Consequently, the Weather Data DPO was removed from the pilot scope.

Regarding DPO 09 (**Cultural Event Schedule of Ano Syros**), the datapack became unnecessary for the evolution phase following the removal of Syros Agenda as a provider, due to open-source availability of the data and the provider’s reluctance to onboard via a connector.

Numerically, that pruning shows up as **datasets identified for sharing decreasing from 10 to 7 (-3)** and **data providers decreasing from 5 to 3 (-2)**, while **non-open datasets drop from 4 to 3 (-1)**—with the weather-related DPO being the most direct contributor to the non-open reduction. At the same time, Table 5 shows a *maturity shift rather than simple shrinkage*: datasets in “**ongoing validation**” **fall from 9 to 4 (-5)** because **three DPOs advance into “completely validated” (0 → 3, +3)** and **two are removed as non-mandatory**, while the single “**just hypothesis**” item disappears (1 → 0, -1) “**Climate Mapping Data of Ano Syros**”.

Risks and mitigation strategies

Risk: Pending validation of UC3 implementation strategy.

Mitigation: A key challenge concerns the feasibility of Use Case 3, specifically regarding potential data consumers for the Gamified experience. The proposed hackathon to deploy UC3 is still under discussion with the coordinator and relevant WP leaders. While this approach could onboard multiple data consumers during the implementation phase, alternative scenarios are being explored in case the hackathon cannot proceed.

Risk: Slower onboarding/data sharing (especially proprietary datasets).

Mitigation: Phased onboarding plans have been established, prioritizing “ready” data feeds first. Common templates for agreements and technical checklists are being used to streamline the process.

Risk: Governance finalisation pending ETDS high-level rules.

Mitigation: Pilot 4 partners will operate under interim governance rules and conduct alignment checkpoints with WP3 to ensure downstream compliance once ETDS rules are finalized.

Risk: Interoperability/technology adoption complexity for providers.

Mitigation: Close coordination with WP2 ensures that partners provide reference deployment patterns and clear integration pathways, reducing technical barriers for data providers.

Risk: Stakeholder’s technical interaction with ETDS.

Mitigation: Clarifications are pending regarding practical data sharing through the ETDS, including data access frequency and compliance with governance protocols. These aspects will be further defined to ensure smooth interactions.

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1.2 Pilot 5 – Empowering SMEs in Tourism through a Collaborative TravelTech

As stated in the previous deliverable, **Pilot 5 – Empowering SMEs in Tourism** aims to strengthen the competitiveness and year-round resilience of tourism SMEs in Lapland by improving their access to and use of shared tourism data. SMEs form the backbone of the regional tourism economy, but face challenges related to strong seasonality, fragmented data, and limited capacity for data-driven decision-making. Within DEPLOYTOUR, the pilot demonstrates how the European Tourism Data Space (ETDS), together with regional data and TravelTech actors, can lower barriers to data sharing and use, and support more sustainable business practices.

Using a needs-based, stakeholder-driven approach, Pilot 5 develops and tests one use case—**Marketing Assistant**—enabling SMEs to plan, test, and evaluate data-driven marketing campaigns that support balanced seasonality and year-round tourism growth. Several potential use cases were identified during M1-M13, and the most feasible one was chosen to be developed at this stage.

1.2.1 Activities carried out and involvement of stakeholders

During the reporting period, Pilot 5 progressed from use case definition toward more concrete preparatory steps, with a focus on data provider engagement and feasibility. Meetings were held with key data providers—The Data Appeal Company, Statistics Finland, and the tourism SMEs in Levi—to confirm data availability and participation in the use case. In parallel, representatives of the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Employment were informed about the project and Visit Finland and Statistics Finland was engaged to ensure alignment and awareness. Following confirmation from data providers, sample data were requested to enable concrete analysis and support the transition from conceptual planning to practical use case development.

To address uncertainties related to data availability and stakeholder readiness, the pilot team developed alternative progression scenarios reflecting stakeholder needs and the current status of identified data sources. Exchanges with WP2 remained ongoing to stay aligned with technological solutions, architectural choices, and overall technical progress within DEPLOYTOUR. This coordination ensures that Pilot 5 advances in line with both practical data access conditions and the common European Tourism Data Space framework. In addition, the pilot has actively followed and aligned with the progress of WP3, particularly regarding data governance, roles, and data-sharing principles.

Use case updates

Number and scope of Use Cases

As concluded in the previous phase, Pilot 5 continues with one Use Case at this stage, as this approach was considered the most effective to clarify and accelerate the pilot implementation. Focusing on a single Use Case responded directly to stakeholder feedback and data source availability, as it represented the highest priority need and strongest interest among participating SMEs and the DMO.

Data providers

During December (M15) - January (M16) the pilot confirmed engagement and availability of key data providers/owners, including The Data Appeal Company, Statistics Finland, Visit Finland and some tourism SMEs in Levi. These tourism SMEs have indicated readiness to participate as data providers; however, their status remains under ‘validation ongoing’ pending detailed sample data assessment and agreements on data-sharing conditions. Discussions focused on data scope, access conditions, and readiness, and sample data were requested to support concrete analysis and implementation.

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Data consumers

The primary data solution users remain tourism SMEs and the destination management organisation (Visit Levi, also an SME).

Data sources

No large changes were made to the overall categories of data sources; instead, the focus shifted toward increasing maturity and feasibility. During the reporting period, the focus shifted from identification to validation and practical feasibility assessment. This means moving from initial identification of potential datasets to confirming provider availability, clarifying access conditions, and requesting sample data to assess technical and governance feasibility for practical use within the Marketing Assistant use case. Identified datasets progressed through validation, with attention to availability, governance conditions, and suitability for practical use within the Marketing Assistant Use Case.

Technical alignment

Coordination with WP2 remained ongoing to ensure that Use Case development stays aligned with technological solutions, architectural decisions, and overall technical progress within DEPLOYTOUR, supporting future interoperability and onboarding pathways.

Use case KPIs

The commented Table below provides Pilot's KPIs measures in M13, M16 and their variation incurred in the quarter.

Table 6. KPIs (Pilot 5)

	M13 (D4.2)	M16 (D4.4)	Variation
KPI 1: Total number of use cases identified	1	1	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	0	0	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	1	1	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Use cases in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
KPI 2: Total number of DATA PROVIDERS identified	11	11	0
<i>Data providers in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	2	0	-2
<i>Data providers in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	9	9	0
<i>Data providers in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	0	2	+2
<i>Data providers in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Data providers in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
KPI 3: Total number of DATASETS identified for sharing	11	11	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	2	0	-2
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	9	6	-5
<i>Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	0	5	+5

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	M13 (D4.2)	M16 (D4.4)	Variation
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
KPI 4: Total number of DATASETS of NON-OPEN DATA identified for sharing	8	8	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: JUST HYPOTHESIS</i>	2	0	-2
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONGOING VALIDATION</i>	6	6	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: COMPLETELY VALIDATED</i>	0	2	+2
<i>Datasets in the phase: ONBOARDING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0
<i>Datasets in the phase: DATA SHARING COMPLETED</i>	0	0	0

Changes in the table are due to datasets and data providers developing from “just hypothesis” to either “ongoing validation” or “completely validated” status. In total, 5 datasets progressed to ‘completely validated’, 2 of which are non-open data.

Risks and mitigation strategies

Risk: Limited resources of tourism SMEs slowing onboarding and data acquisition.

Mitigation: Tourism SMEs operate with limited time and personnel resources, which may slow onboarding processes and participation in data sharing, particularly at early stages of the pilot. To mitigate this risk, WP6 provides targeted training, guidance materials, and capacity-building activities, while the task leader offers hands-on support to participating SMEs. In addition, the pilot deliberately focuses on one single Use Case, ensuring clarity, simplicity, and fast visibility of benefits, which is particularly critical at SME level to maintain engagement and motivation.

Risk: Limited data literacy and technical understanding among SMEs.

Mitigation: Varying levels of data and technical understanding may hinder effective use of shared data and tools. This risk is mitigated through step-by-step onboarding, practical examples, and tailored support delivered through WP6 and the task leader, lowering the threshold for participation and enabling gradual learning through concrete use case implementation.

Risk: Slower progress due to lack of existing data space infrastructure at destination level.

Mitigation: The task leader of Pilot 5 does not operate its own datasets, and the destination does not have an existing data space or ready-to-use technical infrastructure. As a result, progress may be slower compared to pilots that can leverage pre-existing systems. To mitigate this, the pilot adopts a phased and scenario-based approach, prioritising feasible data sources first, requesting sample data to support early validation, and maintaining close coordination with WP2 to align with common architectural solutions and emerging technical pathways within DEPLOYTOUR.

Risk: Dependence on external data providers and proprietary datasets.

Mitigation: Access to proprietary datasets depends on data provider readiness and internal priorities, which may affect timelines. SMEs may hesitate with commitment of resources due to uncertainties on costs and immediate benefits, as well as skill requirements for onboarding. This risk is mitigated by early engagement with data providers, clear clarification of data scope and conditions, and focusing initially on datasets with higher availability and readiness, while continuing negotiations for broader data access.

Risk: Governance and contractual frameworks pending ETDS-level finalisation.

Mitigation: At this stage, formal ETDS membership agreements and standardised data-sharing contract templates are not yet finalised, which may delay full onboarding and operational data exchange. Pilot 5 applies interim governance arrangements, using bilateral

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agreements and agreed principles for sample data exchange, while maintaining regular alignment with WP3 to ensure consistency with emerging ETDS governance.

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Conclusion

This quarterly report (M14–M16, November 2025 – January 2026) demonstrates that **all five DEPLOYTOUR pilots have moved from initial planning into a more structured and operational implementation phase**. Across the Consortium, significant progress has been achieved in consolidating Use Cases' definitions, refining Data Product Offerings (DPOs), validating data providers and datasets, and strengthening alignment with the technical (WP2) and governance (WP3) work packages. The deployment of the Pilot Training Plan, the launch of the Mentoring Programme, and the continuous coordination efforts have provided a **solid framework to support upcoming technical onboarding and governance integration**, in line with the European Tourism Data Space (ETDS) principles.

The next quarterly report, covering the months of February to April 2026 (M17-19), will be delivered in June 2026 and will provide an update on the advancement of use cases validation, technical onboarding, and governance adoption.

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